

Synthesis of Some 2-Arylideneamino-5-Aryl-1,3,4-Thiadiazoles as Potential Fungicides

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Several 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles have been synthesized and condensed with suitable aldehydes in alcoholic medium. The compounds thus obtained were characterized by IR and elemental analysis.

DURING the last three decades, considerable work have been done on various aspects of the chemistry of 1,3,4-thiadiazole compounds. Besides, their use in industry as rubber accelerators¹, corrosion inhibitors for lubricating oils², as pigments for coating³, as preventives of darkening and precipitation in photography⁴ and in the preparation of thermosetting resins and variety of chemotherapeutic applications of thiadiazole compounds have been explored in recent years.

A large number of Schiff's bases are known to have some very useful biological activities, like tuberculostatic^{6,7}, fungicidal⁸ and bacteriostatic activities⁹. Hence Schiff's bases derived from aminothiadiazoles may be considered to have the essential features of both a thiosemicarbazide and an aldehyde and thus may display useful biological activities.

This paper presents the preparation, characterization and fungicidal activities of some 2-arylideneamino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles.

Aroylthiosemicarbazides: Aroylthiosemicarbazides were prepared by the method described by Lora-Tamayo¹⁰. The appropriate acid hydrazide (0.1M) obtained from the appropriate ester (0.4M) and hydrazine hydrate (0.6M) was refluxed with NH₄CN (10g) in ethanolic solution for 4-6 hr. The solutions were cooled and the aroylthiosemicarbazides were isolated. The compounds, prepared in this way, are recorded in Table 1.

2-Amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles: The aroylthiosemicarbazides (0.1M) were treated dropwise with conc. H₂SO₄ (10ml), and the mixtures were neutralized with ammonia and the thiadiazole compounds were precipitated. The compounds were filtered

TABLE 1. AROYL-NH.NH.C—NH₂

S. No.	Aroyl	M.P. (°C)	% yield	Molecular formula	% S		% N	
					Exp.	Calcd.	Exp.	Calcd.
1.	2-Fluorophenyl	108	80	C ₉ H ₆ ON ₃ FS	15.22	15.04	19.02	19.07
2.	3-Fluorophenyl	212	70	C ₉ H ₆ ON ₃ FS	14.84	15.04	19.40	19.70
3.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	215	75	C ₉ H ₆ N ₃ O ₂ S	—	—	—	—
4.	2-Nitrophenyl	210	70	C ₉ H ₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	—	—	—	—
5.	2-Methylphenyl	—	78	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS	—	—	—	—

TABLE 2.

S. No.	Ar	M.P. (°C)	% yield	Mol. formula	% N		% S	
					Exp.	Calcd.	Exp.	Calcd.
1.	2-Fluorophenyl	205	80	C ₉ H ₆ N ₃ FS	21.32	21.12	15.64	15.92
2.	3-Fluorophenyl	214	60	C ₉ H ₆ N ₃ FS	21.15	21.12	15.82	15.92
3.	4-Hydroxyphenyl	—	85	C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ OS	21.42	21.76	16.48	16.57
4.	2-Nitrophenyl	—	95	C ₉ H ₆ N ₄ SO ₂	25.12	25.22	14.25	14.41
5.	2-Methylphenyl	—	68	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S	14.45	14.42	11.20	11.00

TABLE 3. CHARACTERIZATION OF THE SCHIFF BASES

S. No.	Ar ₁	Ar ₂	M.P. (°C)	% yield	Formula	% N		% S		$\nu\text{-N} = \text{C} < \text{cm}^{-1}$
						Exp.	Calcd.	Exp.	Calcd.	
1.	<i>o</i> -methylphenyl	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	121	87	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₃ SCl	13.30	13.40	10.40	10.52	1600
2.	<i>m</i> -fluorophenyl	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	178	58	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₃ SFCl	13.12	13.22	10.04	10.70	1640
3.	<i>o</i> -fluorophenyl	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	155	53	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₃ SFCl	13.12	13.22	10.35	10.70	1690
4.	<i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	<i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	121	80	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	13.98	14.04	10.25	10.70	1670
5.	<i>o</i> -nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	115	73	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₃ S	17.20	17.18	9.45	9.80	1680
6.	<i>o</i> -nitrophenyl	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	198	70	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	16.02	16.20	9.60	9.30	1675
7.	<i>p</i> -methylphenyl	<i>p</i> -nitrophenyl	188	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂ SCl	17.24	17.20	9.20	9.80	1655
8.	<i>o</i> -methylphenyl	<i>p</i> -hydroxyphenyl	184	82	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS	14.25	14.20	10.08	10.80	1660
9.	<i>o</i> -methylphenyl	Furfural	186	75	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ OS	15.20	15.60	12.02	11.98	1635

and recrystallized from liquor ammonia or aqueous ethanol. The prepared compounds are recorded in Table 2.

2-Arylideneamino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles: 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (0.1M) were refluxed with suitable aldehydes for 4 hours in absolute alcohol and the solutions were filtered while hot. The filtrate on cooling deposited crystalline products. The elemental analysis and the stretching frequencies ($\nu\text{-N} = \text{C} <$) are recorded in Table 3.

Evaluation of fungicidal activities: Agar growth technique was employed to evaluate the fungicidal activity of the compounds. This technique involves

the mixing of the toxicant with the agar medium and allowing the planted fungus to grow on such poisoned food. The compounds numbered 1-7 in Table 3 have been tested. The average percentage inhibition by various compounds is given in table 4.

Table 4 clearly indicates that all the compounds are toxic to *Aspergillus niger* at high concentration but most of them showed poor activity upon dilution.

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TABLE 4. FUNGICIDAL ACTIVITY

S. No.	No. of replications	Average percentage inhibition after 96 hr concentrations used	
		1:10,000	1:100,000
1	3	35.4	24.3
2	3	34.2	26.4
3	3	28.4	22.3
4	3	36.4	23.2
5	3	24.8	18.5
6	3	35.2	20.4
7	3	32.0	18.2